

Laser propagation in dense collisional magnetized plasma

K.Li¹ and W.Yu²

¹*Centro De Lasers Pulsados, Salamanca 37185, Spain*

²*Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Science, Shanghai 201800, China*

Dispersion relationship of circularly polarized (CP) electromagnetic wave in collisional magnetized plasma is obtained. The propagation characters of right-hand and left-hand CP into dense collisional magnetized plasma of half-infinite and definite thickness are investigated. The application to inertial confined fusion is discussed and new approach is suggested.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the dispersion relation $\omega^2 = \omega_p^2 + k^2 c^2$ [1], electromagnetic wave (EMW) can only propagate in non-collisional plasma (temperature of electron plasma T is very high) at density below the critical density, $n_e < n_c = 1.1 * 10^{21} \lambda_\mu^{-2} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, where ω is wave frequency, ω_p is plasma frequency, k is wave number, λ_μ is wavelength of wave in μm and n_e is electron plasma density. For relativistic EMW with high intensity $I > 1.37 * 10^{18} \lambda_\mu^{-2} \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$ [2], the critical density becomes γn_c with $\gamma = (1 + I \lambda_\mu^2 / (1.37 * 10^{18}))^{1/2}$ being the relativistic factor. With normalization, this density range can be written as $n = n_e / n_c < 1$. In non-collisional magnetized plasma, the dispersion relation becomes different resulting in different density range [3, 4]. For ordinary wave ($\mathbf{k} \perp \mathbf{B}_0$, $\mathbf{E} // \mathbf{B}_0$), it is $n < 1$; for extraordinary wave ($\mathbf{k} \perp \mathbf{B}_0$, $\mathbf{E} \perp \mathbf{B}_0$), it is $n < 1 + B^{1/2}$; for L wave ($\mathbf{k} // \mathbf{B}_0$, left-hand circularly polarized (LHCP) EMW), it is $n < 1 + B$; for R wave ($\mathbf{k} // \mathbf{B}_0$, right-hand circularly polarized (RHCP) EMW), it is $n < 1 - B$ for $B < 1$ and $n > 0$ for $B > 1$, respectively. Here, \mathbf{B}_0 is magnetic field in plasma, \mathbf{E} is the electric field of EMW, and $B = B_0 / B_c$ is the normalized magnetic field with $B_c = m_e c \omega / e \approx 1.07 * 10^4 \lambda_\mu^{-1}$ Tesla. Thus R wave is reflected by dense plasma ($n > 1 - B$) when $B < 1$, however it can propagate into dense plasma as long as $B > 1$. It should be noted that both n and B are wavelength dependent.

Experimentally, the propagation of R wave in dense plasma was studied only in range of EMW with wavelength much longer than visible light due to the high B_c . For example, it has been studied intensively on low-frequency radio and radar waves propagating in the plasma environments of the ionosphere and magnetosphere of the earth since 1940s [3]. This is because the magnetic field on earth's surface is in the range of $0.25 \sim 0.65$ gauss [5], which corresponds to the radio/radar frequency range of $0.7 \sim 1.8$ MHz. For Nd:YAG laser, which is one of the most powerful laser on earth, the fundamental wavelength of $\lambda_0 = 1.06 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds the extremely high magnetic field of $B_c = 10$ kTesla, which only exists in comic bodies such as magnetar [6] and pulsar [7] currently. Fortunately, the magnitude of artificial magnet has been increasing rapidly during the last decade. Right now, magnetic field as high as 1 kTelsa with mm-size and micro-second-duration has been obtained in (semi) destructive current coil [8] and magnetic field as high as 5 kTesla could be generated by flux compression [9]. It can be anticipated that magnet field above the level of 10 kTesla will come into reality in the not-too-far future.

Theoretically, the propagation of R and L waves into half-infinite dense plasma has been studied analytically in non-collisional plasma and numerically in collisional plasma [10, 11]. However, the basic physic of the propagation of R and L wave in collisional plasma has not been studied yet, especially in plasma with definite thickness. In this paper, the dispersion relation of R and L waves in collisional magnetized plasma will be investigated. The propagation of R wave into dense collisional plasma of half-infinite and finite thickness will be studied. At last, the application of the results will be discussed especially for inertial confinement fusion.

2 PROPAGATION OF CP LASER IN HALF-INFINITE DENSE COLLISIONAL MAGNETIZED PLASMA

To obtain the dispersion relation of R and L waves in collisional plasma, the response of free electrons in field of EMW wave and magnetic field should be obtained. The magnetic field of plasma is written as $\mathbf{B}_0 = B_0 \hat{z}$ and the electric field of harmonic light propagating in plasma is written as $\mathbf{E} = E * \exp(-i\omega t + kz)(\hat{x} - i\sigma \hat{y})$, with $\sigma = -1$ for RHCP and $\sigma = +1$ LHCP. The velocity of free electrons oscillating in RHCP and LHCP wave is $\mathbf{u}_e = u_e(\hat{x} - i\sigma \hat{y})$ with Lorentz force $\mathbf{u}_e \times \mathbf{B}_0 = -i\sigma B_0 \mathbf{u}_e$. The linearized force equation for electron fluid becomes [1]

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_e}{\partial t} = -\frac{e}{m_e} \mathbf{E} - \nu_{ei} \mathbf{u}_e - \frac{e}{m_e} \frac{\mathbf{u}_e}{c} \times \mathbf{B}_0 \quad (1)$$

where $\nu_{ei} \approx 2.9 * 10^{-6} \ln \Lambda n_e Z T^{-1.5}$ is the collisional frequency with n_e being the electron plasma density in cm^{-3} , T being the temperature of plasma in eV, Z being the average charge state of ions and $\ln \Lambda$ being the Coulomb logarithm [1]. The velocity and current of free electrons become

$$\mathbf{u}_e = -\frac{ie/m_e}{\omega((1 + \sigma B_0/B_c) + \nu_{ei}/\omega)} \mathbf{E} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{J} = -n_e e \mathbf{u}_e = \frac{i\omega_{pe}^2}{4\pi\omega((1 + \sigma B_0/B_c) + i\nu_{ei}/\omega)} \mathbf{E} \quad (3)$$

Inserting the current of free electrons into the wave equation of electric field of laser in plasma

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E} - \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_{tt} \mathbf{E} = \frac{4\pi}{c^2} \partial_t \mathbf{J} \quad (4)$$

The dispersion relationship becomes

$$\frac{c^2 k^2}{\omega^2} = 1 - \frac{\omega_{pe}^2/\omega^2}{(1 + \sigma B_0/B_c) + i\nu_{ei}/\omega} \quad (5)$$

The complex permittivity becomes

$$\epsilon_\sigma = 1 - \frac{n}{(1 + \sigma B) + i\nu} \quad (6)$$

with normalized parameters $\nu = \nu_{ei}/\omega$, $n = \omega_{pe}^2/\omega^2 = n_e/n_c$, and $B = B_0/B_c$.

For non-magnetized collisional plasma, the complex permittivity is simplified to $\epsilon = 1 - n/(1 + i\nu)$ same as in the book of Krueer [1]. For magnetized collisionless plasma, the complex permittivity is simplified to $\epsilon_\sigma = 1 - n/(1 + \sigma B)$ same as in the references [3, 4], which is positive for LHCP when $n > 1 + B$ and always positive for RHCP when $B > 1$. For magnetized collisional plasma, the normalized wave vector is $k_\sigma = \sqrt{\epsilon_\sigma} = k_\sigma + i\kappa_\sigma/2$, where k_σ is the real part of refractive index and κ_σ^{-1} is the attenuation length of flux in plasma. The wave equation of electric field is written as

$$E(z) = E * e^{i(k_\sigma z - t)} e^{-\kappa_\sigma z} \quad (7)$$

The propagation of RHCP and LHCP into homogeneous dense collisional magnetized plasma is based on the Fresnel equations [12]. When CP light is normally incident on the interface of vacuum and plasma, the reflection and transmission coefficients of electric field are written as $r_\sigma = (1 - k_\sigma)/(1 + k_\sigma)$ and $t_\sigma = 2/(1 + k_\sigma)$, respectively. For dense collisional magnetized homogeneous plasma with parameters of $n = 100$, $B = 10$, $Z = 3.5$ and $T = 100$ eV, the electric fields of incident, reflected and transmitted RHCP and LHCP with wavelength of $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu m$ are shown in figure 1. Here, n and B are normalized

Figure 1: (a) Electric fields of incident RHCP (solid red), reflected (blue) and transmitted (dashed solid red). Plasma exists at $z > 0$ with $n = 100$, $B = 10$, $T = 100$ eV and wavelength of incident CP is $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu\text{m}$; (b) Same to (a) for incident LHCP.

Figure 2: (a) Dependence of attenuation length of RHCP on magnetic field $B = B_0/B_c$ for $n = 100$ and $T = 100$ eV; (b) Dependence of attenuation length of RHCP on plasma density $n = n_e/n_c$ for $B = 10$ and $T = 100$ eV. In both cases, wavelength of incident RHCP is $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu\text{m}$.

to n_c and B_c at wavelength of $1.064 \mu\text{m}$. It is found that LHCP decays very quickly inside the dense plasma within short distance of $\pi^{-1}(B/n)^{1/2}$ while RHCP has larger attenuation length of κ_σ^{-1} . The wavelength of RHCP inside plasma is $\lambda = (1 + n/(B-1))^{-1/2}\lambda_0 \approx (B/n)^{1/2}\lambda_0$, thus it can be either red shifted or blue shifted, as shown here.

The dependence of attenuation length of RHCP propagating in plasma on the magnetic field and plasma density is shown in figure 2. It is found that RHCP can propagate deeper at higher magnetic field and deposit more energy at higher plasma density. The attenuation length is approximately proportional to $B^{3/2}$, $n^{-3/2}$ and $T^{2/3}$ when $\Gamma \ll 1$, where $\Gamma = \nu/B \approx 1.6ZnB^{-1}T^{-3/2}$ represents the relative effect of collisional absorption and magnetic field. For example, $\Gamma \approx 0.057$ for $n = 100$, $B = 10$, $Z = 3.5$, $T = 100$ eV and $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu\text{m}$. The power reflectivity is independent on plasma temperature for relative high temperature of $T > 100$ eV when $\Gamma \ll 1$.

3 PROPAGATION OF CP LASER IN DENSE COLLISIONAL MAGNETIZED PLASMA FILM

If the above dense plasma has definite thickness, one RHCP laser will be able to propagate through the plasma film when $B > 1$. If the transmitted RHCP is reflected also as RHCP and propagates to

Figure 3: Plasma (gray) is between $z = 0$ and $z = 5 \mu\text{m}$ with $B = 10$ in $z+$ direction, $n = 100$ and $T = 100$ eV. Incident RHCP propagates in $z+$ direction, incident LHCP propagates in $z-$ direction, with same amplitude $a = b = 0.1$ and wavelength $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu\text{m}$. (a) Electric fields of E_0 (solid red), E_1 (dashed red, $z < 0$) and E_4 (dashed red, $z > 0$) from incident RHCP; electric fields of E_0 (solid blue), E_1 (dashed blue, $z > 0$) and E_4 (dashed blue, $z < 0$) from incident LHCP; electric field (solid black) in arbitrary direction of the interference field inside plasma; (b) Energy density of incident RHCP (solid red) and LHCP (solid blue); energy density of reflected RHCP (dashed red) and LHCP (dashed blue); energy density of transmitted RHCP (thick solid red), LHCP (thick solid blue) and their superposition (thick solid black) inside plasma.

the plasma film, the direction of magnetic field looks reversed to it and the plasma becomes opaque when $n < 1 + B$. In this case ($1 + B > n > 1$ and $B > 1$), the dense plasma film becomes a directional optical filter for RHCP. However, if the reflected RHCP is replaced by LHCP, the sign of σ is also reversed. Thus the dense plasma becomes transparent to LHCP propagating in opposite direction as long as $B > 1$. RHCP in $z+$ direction and LHCP in $z-$ direction will interfere inside plasma and deposit more energy inside than one single wave. This phenomenon is quantitatively analyzed below.

The electric fields of RHCP and LHCP propagating in opposite directions are written as $E_0 = E_{i+} = a * e^{iz}$ and $E_0 = E_{i-} = b * e^{-i(z-d)}$, respectively, where d is the thickness of plasma film. Due to the continuity of electric fields and their derivatives of z at the two vacuum-plasma interfaces of $z = 0$ and $z = d$, the electric fields of light inside and outside of plasma film become

$$E(z) = \begin{cases} a * e^{iz} + E_1 * e^{-iz} & z < 0 \\ E_2 * e^{ik_2z} + E_3 * e^{-ik_3z} & 0 < z < d \\ E_4 * e^{i(z-d)} + b * e^{-i(z-d)} & z > d \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$E_1 = -\frac{a(-1 + e^{id(k_2+k_3)})(-1+k_2)(1+k_3) + 2be^{idk_3}(k_2+k_3)}{e^{id(k_2+k_3)}(-1+k_2)(-1+k_3) - (1+k_2)(1+k_3)} \quad (9)$$

$$E_2 = -\frac{2(be^{idk_3}(-1+k_3) + a(1+k_3))}{e^{id(k_2+k_3)}(-1+k_2)(-1+k_3) - (1+k_2)(1+k_3)} \quad (10)$$

$$E_3 = -\frac{2e^{idk_3}(ae^{idk_2}(-1+k_2) + b(1+k_2))}{e^{id(k_2+k_3)}(-1+k_2)(-1+k_3) - (1+k_2)(1+k_3)} \quad (11)$$

$$E_4 = -\frac{b(-1 + e^{id(k_2+k_3)})(1+k_2)(-1+k_3) + 2ae^{idk_2}(k_2+k_3)}{e^{id(k_2+k_3)}(-1+k_2)(-1+k_3) - (1+k_2)(1+k_3)} \quad (12)$$

Here, E_1 represents the electric field of the reflected light from the first vacuum-plasma surface; E_2 and E_3 represent the light propagating inside plasma with same and opposite direction of incident light E_0 , respectively; E_4 represents the transmitted light through plasma film. When E_{i+} is RHCP, both E_2 and E_3 are RHCP with permittivity being $\epsilon_{RH2} = 1 - n/(1 - B + iv)$ and $\epsilon_{RH3} = 1 - n/(1 + B + iv)$. When E_{i-} is LHCP, both E_2 and E_3 are LHCP with permittivity being $\epsilon_{LH2} = 1 - n/(1 + B + iv)$ and $\epsilon_{LH3} = 1 - n/(1 - B + iv)$. Thus, E_{RH2} and E_{LH3} can propagate inside the dense plasma as long as $B > 1$.

If the coherence is assumed to be kept during the collisional propagation inside plasma, RHCP and LHCP in opposite directions will interfere and generate wave with different polarizations, i.e. circularly, elliptically and linearly polarized. Figure 3a shows the electric field inside and outside plasma for incident RHCP in z+ direction and LHCP in z- direction under conditions of $n = 100$, $B = 10$, $T = 100$ eV, $d = 5 \mu m$, $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu m$, and $a = b = 0.1$. For inside plasma, the electric field is of the interference wave in one arbitrary polarization direction. If the coherence is assumed to be totally lost, the energy density inside plasma is the superposition of each from RHCP and LHCP, where the energy density is expressed as $u = |k|^2 EE^*/2$. Figure 3b show the energy density inside and outside plasma in this case with same parameters as in fig 3a.

4 DISCUSSIONS

It is interesting to discuss the application of the above characters on inertial confinement fusion where energy should be deposited to dense plasma. In the scheme of direct drive fusion (DDF), laser is mainly absorbed at density close to the critical density n_c in plasma coronal which is around $100 \mu m$ away from center of compressed fuel, around where the nuclear reactions take place and the density is around $10^4 n_c$ for $\lambda_0 = 1.06 \mu m$ [13, 14]. Efficient energy transport to center of compressed fuel is the main problem for ignition. Energy conduction from coronal to compressed fuel is forbidden due to the mechanism of electron conduction damping. Indirect energy deposition through fast electrons, energetic ions (fast ignition) or shock wave (shock ignition) is being investigated as advanced ignition schemes [14], where laser intensity is high enough to arouse various nonlinear processes in plasma. However, the propagation of R waves is independent on laser intensity, thus direct energy deposition at laser intensity below $10^{14} Wcm^{-2}$ is an promising approach. In this intensity range, the main mechanism of laser plasma interaction is the well-known collisional absorption.

From Lawson criterion, efficient ignition requires the generation of hot spot in deuterium-tritium (DT) fuel with below conditions: $\rho * r > 1 gcm^{-2}$ and $T \simeq 4$ keV, where ρ , r and T are, respectively, the density, radius and temperature of the hot spot [13]. This relationship can be transformed to $n * r_{hs} > 2.2 * 10^6 * \lambda_{\mu}^{-2}$, where n is normalized electron density, r_{hs} is radius of hot spot in μm and λ_{μ} is wavelength in μm . In order that the attenuation length of RHCP/LHCP in hot spot is larger than the radius of hot spot, as shown in fig.3, different conditions are possible with $T = 4$ keV and $\lambda = 1.064 \mu m$, for example, (a) $n = 200$ ($\rho = 1 gcm^{-3}$), $r_{hs} = 1$ cm and $B \geq 100$; (b) $n = 10^3$ ($\rho = 5.2 gcm^{-3}$), $r_{hs} = 2.2$ mm and $B \geq 200$. It is see that laser could be directly deposited to center of fuel with such a low density without pre-compression.

It is also interesting to discuss the application of the results to the existing approaches of laser fusion. In the approach of SI [15], the fuel is first compressed by low intensity laser and then ignited by high intensity laser spike. It can be calculated that magnetic field with the level of $B = 100$ is required to deposit laser almost at the peak density of compressed shell, where the peak density is $n \simeq 1000$, thickness of compressed shell is $d \simeq 50 \mu m$ and temperature is $T \simeq 1$ keV for wavelength $\lambda_0 = 1.064 \mu m$. Because the attenuation length is anti-proportional to the plasma density, RHCP will intrinsically deposit energy at the higher density part, which increaes the efficiency of energy deposition and decreases the propagation distance of shock waves. In the approach of magnetized linear inertial fusion (MagLIF) [16, 17], only two laser pulses and one linear magnetic field are required, which is close to the scheme of fig. 3. Here, the fuel should be first compressed and magnetized, then heated by one RHCP and one LHCP laser. The required magnetic field is around $B = 600$ to obtain the attenuation length of 1 cm for $n \approx 125$, $T = 500$ eV and $\lambda = 1.064 \mu m$, which are the conditions for optimal yield in MagLIF.

The results could also be further investigated at the relativistic laser intensity for target-normal sheath acceleration (TNSA) proton acceleration, the flux of which is required to be greatly increased for ignition. Because the TNSA-proton flux is proportional to the number of accelerated electrons, it can be anticipated that larger flux of proton will be generated when relative RHCP laser propagates into higher density range in magnetized plasma and accelerates larger number of electrons.

5 CONCLUSION

The dispersion relationship of RHCP and LHCP EMW in collisional magnetized plasma is obtained and the propagation of RHCP into dense collisional magnetized plasma is investigated. It is found more energy will be deposit into plasma when RHCP and LHCP from opposite directions irradiate at the plasma film. Such results could be used to directly deposit energy to DT fuel for ignition if the magnitude of magnetic field ($> 10^6$ Tesla) is larger than 10^6 Tesla and could also assist the existing approaches of laser fusion such as SI and MagLIF with high magnetic field.

References

- [1] W. Kruer, *The physics of laser plasma interactions*. CRC Press, 2018.
- [2] W. L. Kruer, "Laser plasma interactions with intensities from 10^{12} – 10^{21} W/cm²," *Physics of Plasmas*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 2087–2092, 2003.
- [3] F. F. Chen and S. E. von Goeler, "Introduction to plasma physics and controlled fusion volume 1: Plasma physics," *Physics Today*, vol. 38, p. 87, 1985.
- [4] Waves in plasmas(n.d.). In Wikipedia. Retrieved September 5, 2018, from. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waves_in_plasmas
- [5] Earth's Magnetic Field(n.d.). In Wikipedia. Retrieved September 5, 2018, from. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Earth%27s_magnetic_field
- [6] Magnetar(n.d.). In Wikipedia. Retrieved September 5, 2018, from. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Magnetar>
- [7] Pulsar(n.d.). In Wikipedia. Retrieved September 5, 2018, from. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pulsar>
- [8] R. Battesti, J. Beard, S. Böser, N. Bruyant, D. Budker, S. A. Crooker, E. J. Daw, V. V. Flambaum, T. Inada, I. G. Irastorza *et al.*, "High magnetic fields for fundamental physics," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1803.07547*, 2018.
- [9] J. Davies. (private communication).
- [10] S. Luan, W. Yu, F. Li, D. Wu, Z. Sheng, M. Yu, and J. Zhang, "Laser propagation in dense magnetized plasma," *Physical Review E*, vol. 94, no. 5, p. 053207, 2016.
- [11] X. Yang, W. Yu, H. Xu, M. Yu, Z. Ge, B. Xu, H. Zhuo, Y. Ma, F. Shao, and M. Borghesi, "Propagation of intense laser pulses in strongly magnetized plasmas," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 106, no. 22, p. 224103, 2015.
- [12] Fresnel equations(n.d.). In Wikipedia. Retrieved September 5, 2018, from. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FresnelEquations>
- [13] O. Hurricane, D. Callahan, D. Casey, P. Celliers, C. Cerjan, E. Dewald, T. Dittrich, T. Döppner, D. Hinkel, L. B. Hopkins *et al.*, "Fuel gain exceeding unity in an inertially confined fusion implosion," *Nature*, vol. 506, no. 7488, p. 343, 2014.
- [14] R. Betti and O. Hurricane, "Inertial-confinement fusion with lasers," *Nature Physics*, vol. 12, no. 5, p. 435, 2016.
- [15] D. Batani, S. Baton, A. Casner, S. Depierreux, M. Hohenberger, O. Klimo, M. Koenig, C. Labaune, X. Ribeyre, C. Rousseaux *et al.*, "Physics issues for shock ignition," *Nuclear Fusion*, vol. 54, no. 5, p. 054009, 2014.
- [16] S. Slutz, M. Herrmann, R. Vesey, A. Sefkow, D. Sinars, D. Rovang, K. Peterson, and M. Cuneo, "Pulsed-power-driven cylindrical liner implosions of laser preheated fuel magnetized with an axial field," *Physics of Plasmas*, vol. 17, no. 5, p. 056303, 2010.
- [17] K. Peterson, "Demonstrating fuel magnetization and laser heating tools for low-cost fusion energy." Sandia National Lab.(SNL-NM), Albuquerque, NM (United States), Tech. Rep., 2016.